

THE BENEFITS OF DEVELOPMENT-LED ARCHAEOLOGY IN EUROPE AND BEYOND

Prepared by the 'Making the case for development-led archaeology' Working Group

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Cover: The site of the Black Death cemetery, with the Tower of London in the background, 1987
Photo: Peter Mills © MOLA

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Summary of legislative instruments governing archaeological heritage management in some member states of the European Archaeological Council. Correct in 2019.

01. INTRODUCTION

Development-led archaeology (also known as preventive, or rescue archaeology) is a fundamental mechanism in helping states across Europe to manage their archaeological heritage. The vast majority of what we learn about our material past derives from investigations in advance of land development. Underpinned by the concepts set out in the European Convention on the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage (Valletta, 1992) (commonly called the [Valletta Convention](#)) and supporting many of the [United Nations Sustainable Development Goals](#), thousands of investigations take place in advance of, or as part of, housing and office development, minerals extraction, and infrastructure improvement each year. The last 30+ years have witnessed extraordinary discoveries and amassed huge volumes of new information about human presence in what is now Europe over the last million years, and the growth of a significant body of highly skilled archaeologists, some in museums, some in research institutes and universities and many in commercial archaeological organisations which now operate in several states. Alongside this growth, professional and ethical standards and guidance have been developed to help ensure that the investigation work is undertaken to high standards. Some states operate licensing systems to underpin this.

The system relies on a clear case of public value. It is essential that the benefits of archaeological investigation and the archives such investigation generates are clearly understood by all the stakeholders, but especially the funders (whether state or private). If those benefits are not recognised, then there is a risk of a loss of support for the system. If the system is undermined, most of the evidence of our common heritage will be lost for ever. Profound changes have already occurred in some states.

Across Europe, we have not been as good as we should have been at explaining these benefits clearly to decision makers, to the funders of archaeology, to archaeologists themselves but most importantly to the general public. This is to be regretted because the arguments for maintaining a proportionately funded development-led archaeological system are very strong and apply in all states across Europe (and beyond).

This document sets out the basis of these arguments as identified by a Working Group of the European Archaeological Council tasked with making the case for development-led archaeology. The arguments are three-fold but interconnected. The first is the cultural and legal argument – that all states already recognise the contribution of their material heritage to society through existing laws and conventions and so should act appropriately. The second is the economic and financial argument – that far from being a burden on public and private finances, properly conducted archaeology is extremely cost-efficient and effective. The third argument is the public benefit argument – that archaeology is a contributor not only to the understanding of our shared past, but to a wide range of other tangible benefits to state, funder, public and archaeologist alike.

In essence, the argument can be summed up as follows: there is a moral, ethical and often legal imperative to make the most of our archaeological heritage. Doing so costs society at large a very small financial price which is considerably more than offset by the full range of benefits that it brings.

This document sets out the evidence for these three arguments in turn and provides case studies to prove the range of benefits identified. The case studies are of investigations which could be repeated in the right circumstances all across Europe, rather than the very special and very extraordinary.

Archaeological heritage managers should be inspired to collect similar case studies in their own states from which to build their own evidence to help ensure the continuity of a very effective system. Archaeological organisations should strive to unlock these benefits more effectively in meaningful dialogue with those who fund their work and those who ultimately benefit – the public at large.

This document forms one of several interlinked resources developed to provide European Archaeological Council (EAC) members with tools to help them manage their archaeological heritage. These tools and resources are as follows:

- The Benefits of Development-Led Archaeology [overview] ([EAC Guidelines 4](#))
- The Value of Developing a Research Framework ([EAC Guidelines 7](#))
- Articulating the Significance of Archaeological Sites ([EAC Guidelines 9](#))

02. THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The recognition of the importance and the consequent management of archaeological heritage across Europe has a deep and complex history¹. But each state has in its own time and its own way, agreed to enact laws which provide the frameworks for managing archaeological heritage.

It is important to reflect upon the fact that the archaeological heritage of all European states is seen by their citizens and leaders as being of such importance that laws should govern how it is managed. Indeed, most states in Europe are now signatories to the key Council of Europe convention, the **European Convention on the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage (1992)** (commonly called the [Valletta Convention](#)).

This defines the archaeological heritage very broadly – “as part of the material heritage in respect of which archaeological methods provide primary information. It comprises all vestiges of human existence and consists of places relating to all manifestations of human activity, abandoned structures, and remains of all kinds (including subterranean and underwater sites), together with all portable cultural material associated with them”². Adopted in January 1992 in Valletta (Malta), it came into force on 25 May 1995 (Council of Europe Treaty Series no. 143). It replaced and updated the original [London Convention of 1969](#), reflecting the change in the nature of threats to the archaeological heritage, which now came less from unauthorised excavations, as was the case in the 1960s, and more from the major construction projects carried out all over Europe from 1980 onwards. It established a body of new basic legal standards for Europe, to be implemented by national policies for the protection of archaeological assets as sources of scientific and documentary evidence, in line with the principles of integrated conservation.

The Convention sets guidelines for the funding of excavation and research work and publication of research findings. It also deals with public access, in particular to archaeological sites, and educational actions to be undertaken to develop public awareness of the value of the archaeological heritage. Finally, the Convention constitutes an institutional framework for pan-European co-operation on the archaeological heritage, entailing a systematic exchange of experience and experts among the various states.

As of 2024, the convention has been ratified by 46 states, which includes 44 Council of Europe member states plus the Holy See. The last signatory to ratify the convention was Luxembourg in 2017. The two Council of Europe states that have not signed or ratified the convention are Iceland and Montenegro. The full list of all signatories can be accessed [here](#).

¹ Just a few examples such as Gillman's 'The Idea of Cultural Heritage' (2006), Thurley's 'Men from the Ministry' (2013) and Svenson's 'The Rise of Heritage: Preserving the Past in France, Germany and England, 1789–1914' (2015) all provide insights into the drivers for, and evolution of, heritage management in various states.

² [European Convention on the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage](#), 1992

As a result of this overarching framework, state legislation across Europe (whether directly linked to the Valletta Convention or reflecting parallel evolution) share common characteristics (see Annex 1):

01. Most states now assert state ownership over all archaeological artefacts when found. This means that those states recognise archaeological remains as a national asset.
02. Many states now require that certain archaeological sites and monuments are given particular legal protection (although the criteria for inclusion on such a 'list' or 'schedule' varies widely between states).
03. Almost all states require that excavation should precede any new development which might damage or destroy archaeological remains.

This has fundamental ramifications. It makes **the state the principal agent for archaeological heritage management**. Archaeologists and developers are not the originators of heritage management, but the actors in a collaborative approach to ensure the best possible public outcome if archaeological remains cannot be preserved where they lie. States generally embrace that responsibility. Mechanisms for provision of funding to discharge this responsibility vary widely across EAC members from centralised state funding through to deregulated private funding. However, regardless of whether the 'developer' of a site is a state-funded or privately-funded organisation, **every state now requires that the developer must contribute to the costs of survey and excavation**.

The Valletta Convention has been enormously successful right across Europe and around the Mediterranean basin, even among states who have yet to ratify it. The scale and quality of archaeological investigation undertaken over the last three decades has been immense and has led to a fundamental transformation of our understanding of the past in every era from the deep palaeolithic to the 20th century, and to outstanding artistic and cultural discoveries which now grace museums everywhere.

The **Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society (2005)**, known as the [Faro Convention](#), also has a significant influence on the way archaeological heritage management is approached among signatory states. The Convention was adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on 13 October 2005, and opened for signature to member States in Faro (Portugal) on 27 October of the same year. It entered into force on 1 June 2011. To date, 24 member States of the Council of Europe have ratified the Convention and 5 have signed it. The full list of signatories is [here](#). Faro is important for its signatories because it amplifies the Valletta Convention's objectives by emphasising the important aspects of heritage as they relate to human rights and democracy. Faro promotes a wider understanding of heritage and its relationship to communities and society and encourages signatories to recognize that objects and places are not, in themselves, what is most important about cultural heritage but that they are important because of **the meanings and uses that people attach to them and the values they represent**.

As a "framework convention" it defines issues at stake, general objectives and possible fields of intervention for member States to progress. Each state party can decide on the most convenient means to implement the Convention according to its legal or institutional frameworks, practices and specific experience. But at the core, it drives the centrality of people – the public – in heritage management, and thus places great focus on extracting public value from archaeological heritage.

In summary, each state has explicitly agreed that responsible archaeological heritage management is a state role and has set out laws and policies to ensure that this happens. This is not for the benefit of archaeologists, academics and specialists but for and on behalf of the people of that state and should therefore provide a clear benefit to those people.

Having established that a clear moral and legal structure exists for states to act to the benefit of their people, it is important to examine what this responsibility costs. Section 3 considers this.

03. ASSESSING THE ECONOMICS OF ARCHAEOLOGY

03.1 INTRODUCTION

Development-led archaeology is dependent upon the construction investments with which it is associated and from which it is funded. Its costs must therefore be sustainable and proportionate. These costs are not well understood and complaints about excessive costs arise from time to time. This can be true both for private investments and public works.

It is therefore important to demonstrate the cost of development-led archaeology in the context of the costs of construction or other forms of land exploitation, and to take a strategic view of these costs. Such evidence will allow evidence-led judgement of proportionality and value for all stakeholders in the process (state governments and decision-makers, investors, archaeologists and, critically, the public).

03.2 THE SURVEY APPROACH

Our agreed approach was to request information about development-led archaeological costs. We chose to use a basic measurement: the number of archaeologists employed in development-led archaeology and their average salary. Because this would not cover all costs (overheads, profit etc), we decided to double the total turnover revealed by our approach.

This gives us a sum for archaeological investment turnover for each state which responded to the survey.

To explore the burden (either on public funding or on private funding, or both) this might impose on the state, we agreed to look at the total construction industry turnover for each state, using published statistics (eg Eurostat). Of course, not every construction project requires archaeological investment – far from it – so our figures are necessarily crude and high-level estimations. But there is no other way to make such a judgement.

The scale and cost of archaeological investment can thus be expressed as a percentage of the total construction investment for each state.

03.3 THE CAVEATS

There are many complexities hidden in this approach which required mediation.

- Some states were unable to provide estimates of average salaries for archaeologists either because the information is protected, or because it is simply unknown. In these cases, we used the national average salary instead. Evidence from an earlier study (Aitchison 2009, 23) suggested that archaeologists were paid roughly between 78% and 122% of national salary, so this does not seem an unreasonable approach.
- States use different workforce models. These are particularly evident in the use of experts and more generalist workforce. This makes the calculation of archaeological costs rather imprecise. To counter this, we have wherever possible used the evidence presented to work out a total archaeological cost, including non-specialist labour.
- The available evidence is out of date, coming from earlier surveys. We have inflated costs but have had to assume that numbers of archaeologists have remained broadly static over the last 5 years.
- The reported construction industry turnover was problematic, as a result of the way in which statistics are presented. We have tried to find the best evidence for the turnover from 2018, but some inaccuracy in the figures may be expected. It is our opinion that such inaccuracies will not change the figures significantly.
- Some states omitted some sub-sectors in reporting construction industry turnover (eg infrastructure or strategic minerals supply) where clearly these do result in archaeological investment. We have tried to determine or estimate from existing data what should be added to the reported numbers. One example was Germany – Nordrhein Westfalen, where the lignite and other minerals extraction market was not included: an estimation based on research on current market was added.

03.4 THE RESULTS

The following chart summarises the results:

There is a broad similarity across member states which responded to the survey, with the majority (70%) falling between 0.04% and 0.14%. The outlying figures for 0.01% in Finland and 0.22% in Germany – Nordrhein Westfalen (labelled Bonn) may warrant closer inspection.

03.5 CONCLUSIONS

Archaeology is not a burden on state economies: The average ‘burden’ of archaeological costs (at 2019) as a proportion of construction turnover is just **0.092%**. That equates to about **€100 for archaeological investment for every €110,000 spent on construction/development**³.

Furthermore, this low economic impact on state economies **assumes no monetisable benefits** arising from development-led archaeology, whereas it is clear that these exist. In Section 4, we explore these benefits in more detail. While these benefits can be articulated readily, we have as yet no way to assess their economic value. However, governments within Europe are transforming their approaches to the valuation of culture and heritage. In the UK for example, the Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) has recently published a framework for Culture and Heritage Capital. It explicitly mentions archaeological resources. This framework, or others like it, may give us the tools to fill this gap.

Culture and Heritage Capital – a logic model (DCMS 2021). In the context of development archaeology, the pressures and interventions are the developments of new buildings, or the exploitation of minerals. The assets (stock) are archaeological sites. The services are the excavations of those assets which create benefits, whose value(s) to the population can be projected.

³In the UK, we know that only 4% of development/construction projects require archaeological considerations of any sort (see www.algao.org.uk/sites/default/files/documents/Archaeology_in_Development_Management.pdf survey). If we were to assume that this is the case across Europe (by no means a safe assumption!), then the average burden on each such project would be 2.14% of project costs. Some states operate a form of hypothecated tax to help even out the cost across all developments.

04. THE PUBLIC BENEFITS OF DEVELOPMENT-LED ARCHAEOLOGY

04.1 INTRODUCTION

The value of archaeology, as a source of knowledge, lies in its capacity to create a bridge to our common past and, as a practice, in its capacity to bring people closer together, excite their appetite for discovery and wonder, and improve their sense of wellbeing. It is a fair criticism that, while archaeological heritage management provides much of the first, it has been less successful in delivering the second.

To redress this imbalance requires a refocus: a fresh look at the whole range of tangible benefits that development-led archaeology can bring and a broader understanding of the importance of these benefits to different stakeholders and audiences. Once each stakeholder group can see the benefits which support their particular interests or concerns, it is more likely that they will support the principles of development archaeology which give them those benefits.

A precondition of explaining the benefits in a straightforward way is to characterise them and to provide clear evidence that they do exist and can be realised. Once we recognise each kind of benefit, we can all seek ways to maximise the chance of creating them. Essentially, we can find ways of 'operationalising' them in the standard approaches to archaeological investigation.

This need not require legislative changes, nor additional funding. Instead, it requires new ways of communicating with the stakeholders and audiences to build projects where the seeking of the full range of benefits is at the heart of the endeavour. Quite clearly, not every investigation will produce all the benefits that have been recognised. By their very nature archaeological investigations are diverse and vary considerably. But, in planning explicitly to seek specific benefits, we should find them more often and be ready to capitalise upon them when we do. The key to success here will be that states ensure all stakeholders (archaeologists, authorities, developers, local communities) collaborate to identify specific benefits at an early stage and embed these intended outcomes into the project design for the investigation. Developers will have their own objectives for public benefit and the archaeology can also be harnessed to respond to many of these.

With such an approach, the combined effect of realising these benefits across each state and over each passing year will propagate and grow the wider social value of archaeology, enriching our knowledge of the past and properly including our citizens in the practice of discovery and knowledge sharing. That in turn will underpin grass-roots support for archaeology and find champions and defenders of the process among developers and investors and within state governments.

What follows is the first step – the characterisation and description of different tangible benefits that we have identified, accompanied by one or two case studies which clearly indicate the nature of each benefit. We recognise that the separation of these different benefits is often artificial, and that several sites can be seen to deliver more than one benefit, but we believe the classification helps with understanding. We have also offered our view of where these benefits support the [UN Sustainable Development Goals](#).

We have deliberately chosen case studies which are likely to be replicable, rather than unique to particular circumstances. We have also looked across the breadth of EAC membership to show that the principles hold true regardless of different state legal or policy frameworks.

We anticipate and encourage each state to develop a library of its own case studies, perhaps using the format we have adopted, as these will be more persuasive and accessible to local stakeholders.

04.2 BENEFIT 1: EVIDENCE OF SHARED HISTORY

Development-led archaeology makes a fundamental change to our understanding of the past and our shared history.

Archaeology offers the means to understanding the past and our shared history. This lies at the root of successive heritage legislation enacted by governments over most of two centuries, and at the heart of successive international treaties and charters. Shared understanding of where we come from is a cohesive force for all citizens of the world and can work at a local or a global level. Development-led archaeology now drives the vast majority of this new understanding. It contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goals 4 (quality education) and 16 (peace, justice and strong institutions).

Our case studies demonstrate the impact two sites can have on the understanding of human urbanisation, technological development, and creativity and the spread of world religions.

CASE STUDY:

Ribe, Denmark – The Spread of Christianity in Scandinavia

In 2000, a fire destroyed a house, located in the historic centre of Ribe, Denmark. Afterwards, what remained of the building was demolished and the remaining debris was removed, thus creating an open building plot, just south of the cathedral and owned by the parish. Soon, plans were made to erect a new building. This implied an obligation by law (2002) to take care and responsibility of the archaeological heritage on the site. With an expectation of approximately 3.5m of archaeological stratigraphy on a highly interesting location, this was a financially challenging task. Through the financial support of the philanthropic association Realdania, preliminary excavations were conducted by the Museum of Southwest Jutland (Sydvestjyske Museer) in area of circa 150m² in 2008-2009. The goal was to gain insight into the preservation conditions of the site and in the nature of the archeology. During the preliminary excavation, Christian graves were discovered from the 9th, 10th and 11th century.

The dating of these graves astounded the researchers. From historical records, it was known that Christian missionary work had been performed in Denmark by Ansgar ("Apostle of the North") in the 9th century, but it remained unclear what the exact impact of this mission was. The discovery of Christian graves from that period, confirmed that indeed a Christian minority had settled in Ribe a full century before Christianity became Denmark's state religion.

Excavations at Kannigaarden, Ribe.

© Morten Søvsø, Head Curator,
Archaeology & Collections,
Museum of Southwest Jutland
(Sydvestjyske Museer).

The results of the first excavations on the plot also excited the parish and thus the owner of the plot. The parish embraced the archaeological site as 'their' heritage (see Benefit 4 below) and was keen on gaining more knowledge on their own common past. Therefore, they specifically chose to expand the excavations instead of preserving the site in situ. Also, the topography of the site made it very difficult to construct a building and protect all the archaeology below. Thus, the obligated additional financial resources were provided to the Museum of Southwest Jutland and the excavation was expanded up to a total of 400m² between 2011 and 2012.

Again, the research resulted in finds of great interest. One of the (if not the) oldest brick-built houses in Denmark: the remains from the canons' monastery dating back to the 12th century. The ruin was listed as a monument and therefore needed to be preserved. Crucially, this was not seen as a problem by the developers and their architects (Lundgaard & Tranberg Architects), but as an opportunity for communicating the many cultural historic layers of the location with the public and as a source of inspiration for the design of the new building. This new building consists of a single, oblong volume with a pitched roof, supported by pillars above the preserved archaeological findings. In 2017, it was nominated as one of the five finalists of the European Union Prize for Contemporary Architecture - Mies van der Rohe Award. Plans were developed to communicate with the public about the early Christian graveyard and an English publication about the archaeology of Ribe was published in 2022.

The award shortlisted Kannigegaarden Hall, Ribe, influenced by the archaeology. © Anders Sune Berg for Lundgaard & Tranberg Architects.

Publications, links, resources

Coming up: Ribe 700-1050 – from Emporium to Civitas in Southern Scandinavia (2020, Jutland Archaeological Society)

Morten Søvsø, 'Ansgars Kirche in Ribe', in Rainer-Maria Weiss and Anne Klammt (eds), *Mythos Hammaburg. Archäologische Entdeckungen zu den Anfängen Hamburgs*, Veröffentlichung des Helms-Museums, Stadtmuseum Harburg Nr. 107, Archäologisches Museum Hamburg, 2014.

About the architecture and the exhibition of the archaeological site:

www.archdaily.com/804321/kannikegarden-lundgaard-and-tranberg-architects

Søren Sindbæk (ed) *Northern Emporium: Vol. 1 The making of Viking-age Ribe*, Jysk Arkæologisk Selskabs Skrifter, Århus University Press 2022

CASE STUDY:**Amiens-Renancourt, France – Possible Upper Palaeolithic sculpture workshop**

The prehistoric site of Renancourt, in Amiens has been known for many years and long remained one of the few sites providing evidence for human presence in northern France during the Early Upper Palaeolithic (35,000 – 15,000 BP). Near the confluence of the Selle and Somme Valleys, the site known as Amiens-Renancourt 1 – a probable hunting camp – was discovered in 2011, during an Inrap diagnostic operation, and has been excavated since 2014. Four meters below the current ground level, a concentration of very well-preserved artifacts was discovered, Carbon-14-dated to 23,000 BP, attributed to a late phase of the Gravettian culture, which was present in Europe between 28,000 and 22,000 years ago.

The abundant artifacts reveal the diverse activities practiced at this hunting camp. Among the numerous flint artifacts, projectile points (Gravette Points) were used for hunting, while large blades were transformed into other tools, such as knives and scrapers. Abundant bone remains show that horse meat was regularly consumed. In the full glacial period, this Gravettian hunting camp appears to have been occupied for a few weeks at the end of the warm season, just before autumn.

Venus aux cheveux decouverte en 2019 a Amiens-Renancourt. © Stephane Lancelot, Inrap.

However, in 2014 a "Venus" figurine was found, carved from chalk. It was the first to be found in northern France, excavated in 19 fragments and measuring 15cm high. Remarkably it turned out to be the first of 15 of these statuettes revealed at the site. The last, found in 2019 is an exceptional discovery and increased this site's international significance. This near-complete "Venus" sculpture, some 23,000 years old, 4 centimeters tall, is steatopygic: the volume of the rear, thighs and breasts is hypertrophied. The arms are barely present, and the face is represented without lines. It adheres perfectly to the aesthetic canon of the Gravettian stylistic tradition, which includes the Venuses of Lespugue (Haute-Garonne) and Willendorf (Austria), as well the bas-relief Venus of Laussel (Dordogne). This "Venus" of Renancourt also has a surprising "hairdo" represented by a grid pattern of thin incisions similar to those of the Venus of Willendorf and, especially, of the Venus of Brassempouy (Landes), also known as the "Lady with a Hood."

More remarkably, the archaeologists suspect this site was a workshop for the production of these sculptures as they are accompanied by several thousands of chalk fragments, some of which appear to be manufacturing waste products. Furthermore, personal ornaments have also been found here, such as the unique perforated disks in chalk.

The significance of this site for understanding the context of such sculptures, their mode of creation and their relationship with other activities at what is believed to be a temporary hunting camp are immediately apparent, making Amiens-Renancourt 1 a hugely important site for understanding this remote time in our past.

Publications, links and resources

www.inrap.fr/en/paleolithic-venus-discovered-amiens-14792

Paris, C, Deneuve, E, Fagnart, J-P, Coudret, P, Antoine, P, Peschaux, C, Lacarrière, J, Coutard, S, Moine O et Guérin, G 2017 'Premières observations sur le gisement gravettien à statuettes féminines d'Amiens-Renancourt 1 (Somme)', Bulletin de la Société préhistorique française, Tome 114, numéro 3, Juillet-Septembre 2017, p 423-444

04.3 BENEFIT 2: NATIONAL CULTURAL TREASURES

Development-led archaeology discovers and secures outstanding artistic or cultural treasures for permanent display to the public.

Tourism statistics demonstrate the pulling power of particular forms of heritage – our landscapes, archaeological monuments, and outstanding artistic or cultural treasures on permanent display to the public. The list of these treasures is not static – it grows through discovery, and flourishes through understanding, public engagement and interaction. It is a gift to the future from the past. Development-led archaeology makes an enormous contribution. It contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 (quality education).

Our case studies demonstrate the capacity to save fragile 7000-year-old fishtraps, exquisite Roman statues and even a temple itself for the public.

CASE STUDY:

Clowanstown, Ireland – Mesolithic Fish Baskets

A series of well-preserved wooden baskets was discovered at Clowanstown, Co. Meath in Ireland in 2007, at a site excavated as part of advance archaeological investigations for the M3 Clonree–North of Kells motorway scheme. The excavations were carried out on behalf of Transport Infrastructure Ireland (then National Roads Authority) and Meath County Council by Archaeological Consultancy Services Ltd. The earliest structures identified on-site are the remains of a Late Mesolithic mooring/fishing platform and the remains of conical fish baskets.

3D digital model of the fish basket. © National Museum of Ireland

The site at Clowanstown was located on the edge of a raised bog, which at the end of the last Ice Age would have been a small lake. During the Mesolithic period (7500–4000 BC) people subsisted by fishing, hunting and foraging. Clowanstown would have provided an ideal location for these activities as fish and waterfowl were available from the lake. However, evidence in Ireland for the presence of these early settlers is often very elusive - the people who lived at that time mainly used organic materials for structures and objects of everyday life, which as a result are generally perishable and rarely survive to the present day.

In this context, the revelation of a beautifully preserved basket was an extraordinary and unexpected discovery. The first basket, over a meter in length, tapered from a wide to a narrow, pointed end which had become flattened over time. It returned a radiocarbon date of 5210–4970 BC. Following on from the initial discovery, four more baskets of the same form were discovered at similar levels on-site.

Basketry and organic materials from the early prehistoric period are exceptionally rare in Ireland, with only five known examples surviving. The significance of the Clowanstown traps lies not only in the fact that they now form the largest section of the national assemblage of organic material for the Mesolithic period in Ireland but also for the information they add to our knowledge of economy, subsistence and craft for this period. The baskets are on permanent display in Ireland's National Museum.

Fish baskets on display in the museum. © National Museum of Ireland

The baskets present the positive contribution of development-led archaeology to an audience of over 500,000 annual visitors. Positioned at the beginning of the visitor's exploration of Ireland's material heritage, they promote awareness of the growing diversity of the archaeological resource. They illustrate how development-led archaeology funding of new sciences led to rare organic materials not only being preserved but stabilised for public display. The fish trap continues to feature in engagement and educational programmes which promote Irish archaeology to a wide range of domestic and international audiences. It illustrates the modern approach to develop-funded archaeological mitigation and acknowledges the roles played by archaeologists and conservators in ensuring that these fragile treasures are preserved for posterity.

Due to their importance and fragility, the baskets were laser scanned in advance of conservation to produce extremely accurate 3D digital records of each of the fish traps. Through the resulting computer models the fish traps are preserved and archived for the future and can now be studied without any risk to the artefacts themselves.

Publications, links, resources

[Imagining archaeology through art - \(tii.ie\)](#)

[Seanda, Issue 2, 2007 \(English version\)](#)

[Seanda, Issue 4, 2009 \(English version\) \(tii.ie\)](#)

[100 Objects](#)

[1-Read_Mesolithic_Fish_Trap_V2.pdf \(100objects.ie\)](#)

doi.org/10.7486/DRI.3485bx67k

[Archaeological excavation report, E3064 Clowanstown 1, County Meath. | Europeana](#)

CASE STUDY:**The Mithraeum, London, England**

The Roman Mithraeum or Temple of Mithras in London was first discovered in 1954 during redevelopment works. On the last day of its excavation, a sculpted head of Roman god Mithras was found. The discovery was featured in newspapers and the planned destruction of the site was aborted. The intense public interest prompted the authorities and the developer to give the archaeologists a few more weeks to excavate and the site was opened for the visitors after working hours. Tens of thousands of people queued on the streets to see the temple. Found within it, where they had been carefully buried at the time of its rededication from Mithras to Bacchus in the early 4th century, were finely detailed third-century white marble likenesses of Mithras, Minerva, Mercury the guide of the souls of the dead, and the syncretic gods and Serapis, imported from Italy. There were several coarser locally-made clay figurines of Venus, combing her hair. The temple was deconstructed and reassembled c.100 m from its original location for public display in 1962, while the remarkable statuary recovered from the temple was put on display and is now in the Museum of London. The reconstructed Temple was designated a Listed Building in 2007 due to being one of the first examples of development-related archaeological conservation.

In 2010 the Bloomberg company purchased the Walbrook Square development site for its new European headquarters. There were a complex series of planning-related requirements placed on the development, due to the archaeology expected beneath the site and the Listed Temple. Conditions placed included the removal and reconstruction of the Temple in as close to its original location as could be arranged given that some of the original remains remained in situ. Unusually, the City of London Corporation also included a Condition relating to public engagement during the excavations, enabling public access to the site, an oral history project on the 1950s excavations, and much digital coverage. Archaeological and reconstruction works took place 2010-2014 and have resulted in a modern reconstruction of the temple and an exhibition space⁴.

The Tauroctony (slaughter of the bull) found on the site of the temple in 1889, before the temple itself was recognised.

© Museum of London.

⁴ data.bloomberglp.com/company/sites/30/2017/11/BLA-web.pdf

The finished Mithraeum display, publicly accessible beneath the new Bloomberg building.
© Carol Raddato.

While the reconstruction of a Roman temple and its re-siting under a new office block is not likely to be within the scope of most development budgets for archaeology, this case study is important because of the sequence of public interactions with their past. As well as the opportunity for thousands to visit the site in 1954, and the recovery of a stunning group of statues placed on display in the Museum of London, at the time of the temple's relocation an oral history project was conducted with 29 surviving interviewees who had been present at the original 1954 public opening. The Mithraeum-related memories of the project participants were positive: many remember the excitement in seeing the ruins before they were to be demolished. The temple was considered to be a valuable remnant of London's past, worthy of protection in the post-war rebuilding of the City, and the queuing added to the experience of anticipation. The interviews and other material are recorded and stored with the Archaeology Data Service and with [Bishopsgate Institute](#) in London. At the end of the project, an event brought all the participants together and presented them the collected memories and archaeological finds. At the event, there were young WORLDwrite journalists interviewing and recording the guests who had visited the site in 1950s. This resulted in many new social connections and WORLDwrite volunteers produced a 23-minute film of the event.

This complex case study demonstrates the increasing public benefit from display of discoveries and artefacts. The interviews, some 60 years after the event, revealed that the lasting impact of the visit to the excavation site, confirmed that it had sparked people's further interest in archaeology and that interest was often passed on to younger generations; some of the visitors had even become archaeologists or archaeology academics partly as a result. The relationship between access, interaction, display and memory is, or should be an important consideration in development-led archaeology and can be a positive benefit to all stakeholders involved. The commitment to ensuring the public benefit was achieved on the part of the curatorial teams across the City of London and Historic England resulted in engagement at all stages of the project and encouraged the client Bloomberg to understand the value of using archaeology in this way. The Mithraeum is freely accessible to all, and has proved to be a highly successful addition to London's ancient built heritage.

Publications, links, resources

MOLA 2016. Remembering the Temple of Mithras. An oral history project, Bloomberg London. Report. Accessible at: www.academia.edu/37399980/Remembering_the_Temple_of_Mithras_An_oral_history_project_Bloomberg_London

www.bajrfed.co.uk/bajrpress/remembering-londons-roman-temple-of-mithras/

data.bloomberglp.com/company/sites/30/2017/11/BLA-web.pdf

www.londonmithraeum.com/

04.4 BENEFIT 3: STORIES OF DISCOVERY AND DEBATE

Development-led archaeology creates major news stories reaching large numbers of citizens.

Archaeology engages people in emotive and genuine ways. New discoveries create excitement; experiencing heritage promotes debate. Archaeology is the tangible presence of past personal, family or community memories. Archaeology encourages people to talk and share. Talking and sharing encourages action and engagement, from the simplest question from a member of the public “Have you found anything interesting?” to major news stories which encircle the globe. Development-led archaeology stories can forge a link between the developer and the community. It contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goals 4 (quality education) and 16 (peaceful, justice and strong institutions).

Our case studies show the power of a Roman river barge and a medieval ossuary to capture world-wide media attention.

CASE STUDY:

Utrecht, Netherlands – Cool digging days / Gave Graafdagen

In 1997 west of Utrecht, one of the main cities in the Netherlands, a major urban development started, aiming to create as many as 30,000 new houses. One of the underlying principles of the development was to make optimal use of the qualities of the historic environment. The urban planners carefully integrated the basic framework and many markers of the cultural landscape, not just the scheduled monuments, but also historic roads, water courses, remains of the local orchard and greenhouse horticulture, archaeological sites, etc⁵. In advance of the development a total of 120 excavations were carried out. As the area was part of the Lower German limes, about one third of the excavated sites concern the Roman period. With the limes road as a guide, the fieldwork programme soon located, and focused on, structures to do with water management, building logistics as well as control and communication, notably including several watchtowers⁶.

There were also numerous ship-finds, of which the Meern I is probably the most famous. A 24.6m long ship with a cabin, built around 148 AD, it is remarkable for containing one of the most complete inventories ever found aboard a Roman river vessel, including chests, tools and a galley. At first it was decided to leave the ship in-situ, but when this turned out to be impossible because of risks for the conservation of the ship the municipality decided to excavate it⁷. Excavations were carried out in 2003.

⁵ Spangenberg, Ph. ed., 1995: Masterplan Leidsche Rijn, Amsterdam.

⁶ Enckevort, H. van, Hazenberg, T, Vos, W.K., Graafstal, E.P. & Polak, M., 2006: Die Grenze in den Niederlanden. In: G. Klose & A. Nünnerich-Asmus eds. Grenzen des Römischen Imperiums (Zaberns Bildbände zur Archäologie), Mainz.

⁷ After a 10-year conservation treatment the ship was finally brought back to Utrecht and is now on display in Castellum Hoge Woerd www.castellumhogewoerd.nl

During the excavations open days were held. These were called the “cool digging days” (gave graafdagen). This created a huge amount of publicity. Along with the dig, activities were set up in order to make the archaeology accessible, visible and tangible for a wider audience, to position the city of Utrecht as a city of archaeology and to make the habitants of the neighbourhood aware and proud of the “old land”⁸:

- (pre)publicity and intensive press contacts around the start of the project, the educational program, the opening of the “week for the public” and the excavation and lifting and transport of the ship.
- Information at the site
- Opening day
- Travelling small exhibition
- Information in the neighbourhood library
- Organisation of a “week for the public” (including the “cool digging days”)
- Educational program

The ‘cool digging days’ attracted over 30,000 visitors. Photo courtesy Hans Theunissen.

The combined activities generated the attention of national as well as local newspapers, specialized magazines such as the magazine of the Royal Dutch Tourist Association (ANWB), local and national news, radio and media sites. The ‘cool digging days’ attracted over 30,000 people in only two weekends, of whom 77% were local and regional visitors, 20% visitors from other parts of the Netherlands and even a few international visitors⁸. Visitors told the archaeologists that the news about the finding of the ship and the open days was “everywhere”.

Media attention didn’t end here. The story kept coming back, when the ship was brought to the conservation station, when conservation was finished and finally when the ship arrived back in Utrecht to be exhibited in Castellum Hoge Woerd, a museum, visitors-, neighbourhood- and nature education centre that was built on a Roman Castellum site (listed monument) to represent the local Roman past.

Publications, links, resources

Graafstal, E.P.: Castellum Hoge Woerd (Utrecht-NL): a revived Roman fort based in the local community. To be published in Public Archaeology in 2021.

Hazenberg Archeologie Leiden bv, 2004: Eindrapport publieksenquête Gave Graafdagen, Leiden.

Spangenberg, Ph. ed., 1995. Masterplan Leidsche Rijn, Amsterdam.

Enckevort, H. van, Hazenberg, T, Vos, W.K., Graafstal, E.P. & Polak, M., 2006: Die Grenze in den Niederlanden. In: G. Klose & A. Nünnerich-Asmus eds. Grenzen des Römischen Imperiums (Zaberns Bildbände zur Archäologie), Mainz.

www.leidscherijninbeeld.nl/?tag=gave-graafdagen

www.castellumhogewoerd.nl

⁸ Hazenberg Archeologie Leiden bv, 2004: Eindrapport publieksenquête Gave Graafdagen, Leiden.

⁹ Hazenberg Archeologie Leiden bv, 2004: Eindrapport publieksenquête Gave Graafdagen, Leiden.

CASE STUDY:**Saint Bavo Cathedral, wall of bones, Flanders**

The Saint Bavo Cathedral holds the famous Ghent Altarpiece (or the Adoration of the Mystic Lamb), painted by Hubert and Jan van Eyck. The altarpiece is undergoing restoration and will be placed in a new show case in 2024. Accompanying works to the buildings will permit greater visitor numbers and provide far better access for disabled people. In the garden of the cathedral (part of the former cemetery), construction of a new visitor centre led to detailed archaeological excavations which concluded in 2020. During the excavations, more than 1,000 skeletons were excavated. While these generated local media interest in Flanders, the discovery of a number of 'walls' made from (mainly) human leg bones and dated to the 15th or 16th centuries attracted international attention.

Much of this attention was doubtless created by the public's fascination with death and the macabre, but many of the reports avoided sensationalisation and explored the implications of the bone walls in the context of past approaches to disturbing the dead and reintering their remains.

The 'wall of bones' under excavation at St Bavo Cathedral. © Ruben Willaert NV

It is useful in this case study to show the considerable and widening impact of the news story. It first got picked up by 'national' television and radio news and the largest Flemish newspapers:

- www.vrt.be/vrtnws/nl/2020/02/14/muurtjes-van-dijbenen-en-scheenbenen-ontdekt-tijdens-opgravingen/
- www.nieuwsblad.be/cnt/dmf20200213_04847727
- www.hln.be/in-de-buurt/gent/straffe-ontdekking-muren-uit-beenderen-en-schedels-onder-sint-baafskathedraal-a21a4d56/
- De Standaard: api-production.gopress.be/storage/get/id/2020-02-14%7C%7C2411%7C%7Cpage29.pdf/hash/250178f95fb7eef29ee5982632aeb31-17be97660961ca3b544209aea26771b37fdc7a83/token/ca5b28df3a504d5e1c239fdcedbdf099e884251581667800/

These locally published stories were then picked up by a newsletter for English speakers living in Brussels:

- www.brusselstimes.com/all-news/belgium-all-news/94984/walls-made-of-human-bones-discovered-under-ghent-cathedral-graveyard-thigh-shin-skulls-catacombs-van-eyck/

After that, it spread to other countries:

The Netherlands:

- archeologieonline.nl/nieuws/archeologen-ontdekken-muren-van-menselijke-botten-in-gent
- www.pzc.nl/gent/straffe-ontdekking-muren-uit-beenderen-en-schedels-onder-sint-baafskathedraal-a21a4d56/?referrer=https://www.google.com/

UK:

- www.mirror.co.uk/science/creepy-wall-made-human-bones-21514343
- www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-8013527/Wall-human-bones-skulls-dates-500-years-ago-Belgian-cathedral.html
- www.thesun.co.uk/tech/10965688/wall-human-bones-cathedral-belgium/
- The Independent (UK): www.independent.co.uk/news/world/europe/belgium-saint-bavo-cathedral-human-bones-archaeologists-a9341616.html
- IFL Science (UK): www.iflscience.com/editors-blog/medieval-wall-made-of-human-bones-discovered-in-belgium/
- www.express.co.uk/news/science/1243788/archeology-news-wall-human-bones-skulls-discovery-belgium

USA:

- www.foxnews.com/science/wall-made-from-human-bones-and-skulls-belgian-cathedral
- www.msn.com/en-us/sports/mlb/wall-made-using-human-bones-and-skulls-found-under-cathedral/vp-BB1062zo

France:

- www.rtl.fr/actu/international/belgique-des-murs-d-os-ont-ete-decouverts-sous-la-cathedrale-de-gand-7800141929
- www.lefigaro.fr/cinema/des-murs-faits-d-os-humains-decouverts-pres-de-la-cathedrale-de-gand-en-belgique-20200222

Italy:

- www.lastampa.it/viaggi/mondo/2020/02/24/news/il-mistero-della-cattedrale-belga-con-le-fondamenta-fatte-di-ossa-umane-1.38510102

Spain:

- www.lavanguardia.com/cultura/20200221/473677279836/paredes-huesos-humanos-adultos-catedral-gante-san-bavon-belgica.html

And then made it into archaeological magazines and science websites:

- www.archaeology-world.com/walls-made-of-human-bones-discovered-under-ghent-cathedral/
- www.archaeology.org/news/8475-200221-belgium-bone-walls
- archaeologynewsnetwork.blogspot.com/2020/02/walls-made-of-human-bones-discovered.html
- www.livescience.com/bone-walls-belgium-church.html
- www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/walls-made-ancient-human-leg-bones-unearthed-beneath-church-belgium-180974255/
- www.ancient-origins.net/news-history-archaeology/bone-walls-0013317
- en.geneanet.org/genealogyblog/post/2020/02/wall-made-of-human-bones-and-skulls-that-dates-back-500-years-ago-is-unearthed-by-archaeologists-at-a-belgian-cathedral
- www.geo.fr/histoire/des-archeologues-decouvrent-des-murs-dos-sous-une-cathedrale-en-belgique-200043

It went on to appear in many other online news sites. The importance of this case study is that it shows how a relatively minor discovery (in archaeological terms) can act as a hugely powerful catalyst to generate world-wide interest in not only the discovery itself, but also in the development work that led to it.

04.5 BENEFIT 4: SOURCES OF COMMUNITY PRIDE

Development-led archaeology enhances communities.

Communities are often (and rightfully) very proud of their archaeological heritage. Archaeology can be a force-multiplier for enhancing community identity. Places can become inspirational, aspirational and sources of significant pride. Community identity can be bolstered by investment and co-creation centred around much-loved or storied discoveries, monuments and settings. Development-led archaeology contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goal 11 (sustainable cities and communities).

Our case studies show the capacity for excavations to reincarnate a functioning public theatre in its Roman structure, and to shape the identity of a community and its school.

CASE STUDY:

The Impact of Amesbury Archer School, Wiltshire, UK

In 2002, Wessex Archaeology undertook excavations (funded by Bloor Homes and Persimmon Homes South Coast) in advance of construction of a large housing development, associated school and a community centre. The level of regular and informed communication between the archaeologists and the developer greatly enhanced the potential of various aspects of the project and ensured that the developer was fully appraised of how the archaeology could be an opportunity rather than a hindrance.

The excavations uncovered the burial of a man dating to 2,300 BC, who became known as the 'Amesbury Archer'. The Archer was a major discovery for several reasons. His was one of the most-well-furnished, if not the most, Bell Beaker grave in Europe and so of international significance, as well as containing the earliest evidence for both gold and copper in Britain. Isotopic analysis of his skeleton demonstrated for the first time that individuals did travel long distances in prehistory and revealed that he had travelled from the area around the Alps as part of the early representations of the Bell Beaker culture, perhaps part of the emerging elite. The burial was found a few kilometres from Stonehenge and possible link with the site caught the public interest. A programme of analysis by Wessex Archaeology included leading authorities from outside the organisation and provided a scholarly monograph as well as accessible content for the internet, Salisbury Museum and other outputs such as the prospectus for the school built on the site.

A series of innovative decisions were made by various stakeholders; for example *The Amesbury Archer School* name came from the Local Education Authority; the name for a nearby local pub on the Solstice Park development came from a public competition (also *The Amesbury Archer*) and the name for the community centre (*The Bowman Centre*, named after a collective burial found during the development) came through the planning process. The discovery of the Archer burial redefined many aspects of the project, including the name for the wider scheme: *Archer's Gate*.

The discovery also resulted in the addition of the Archer onto the National Curriculum for Key Stage 2 (ages 7-11), which in turn generated online and other educational materials from organisations including the BBC and the Times Educational Supplement. The school pupils, Wessex Archaeology specialists and local museums were involved with the design of a sculpture of the Archer: 'Fire and Iron' during which '*...themes emerged of heritage, continuation, parallels, family, disability, metals, ancient symbols, modern cures and the interpretation of fragmented clues*' (quote from Fire and Iron webpage)

The school embedded learning about the Archer and said '*we have embraced the story of his journey from the mountains to the plains of Stonehenge as a learning model for our school. We are proud to be called Amesbury Archer Primary School and to follow in his unique historical footprint*', with classes given archaeological names and the school's logo designed by the archaeological team.

The larger development that Amesbury Archer school sits within adopted its archaeological past in other areas, such as the pub and the community centre. The benefit provided by a context such as the Archer burial is unique to archaeology, as it is only through excavation 'on the ground' that we can provide such an authentic opportunity for place-making. Although it is clearly a nationally significant discovery it is not the only such discovery, but it was the one where all the various stakeholders saw the positive opportunities and collaborated to achieve them.

The full adoption of the Archer and archaeology more generally into the learning mission for the school has given them a focus and a sense of pride in their local area. The benefit of this is felt particularly strongly within the local community, the school pupils and their families. The impact of having the Archer in national educational curricula is certainly significant, and his story forms part of learning for 7-11 year olds across England.

The school's name board. © Elaine Wakefield, Wessex Archaeology.

There are also indications that the discovery in 2002 has continued to be an influence over subsequent developments in the area, with areas incorporating archaeological content in their names and open space design.

The speed and strength of the publicity surrounding the findings enabled the early deposition of artefacts in the Salisbury Museum, making them available to the wider public.

Publications, links, resources

Wessex Archaeology web pages: www.wessexarch.co.uk/our-work/amesbury-archer

Monograph: Fitzpatrick, A, 2011, The Amesbury Archer and the Boscombe Bowmen. Bell Beaker Burials at Boscombe Down, Amesbury, Wiltshire, Salisbury, Wessex Archaeology Report 27 (reprinted in paperback 2013).: www.wessexarch.co.uk/our-work/amesbury-archer-and-boscombe-bowmen

Amesbury Archer School prospectus: www.amesburyarcher.wilts.sch.uk/docs/Prospectus.pdf

Jayne Brayne author/artist web pages and background to book: janebrayne.wordpress.com/amesbury-archer/

Tim Peake and the Amesbury Archer: janebrayne.wordpress.com/2016/06/18/tim-peake-and-the-amesbury-archer/

Fire and Iron sculpture: www.fireandiron.co.uk/amesbury-archer

CASE STUDY:**Plovdiv, Bulgaria – Roman Theatre**

Plovdiv, formerly known as Philippopolis, is one of the oldest cities in Europe. The remains of the Roman city lie underneath the modern city centre and there are several well-preserved structures found, excavated, and exposed. The Roman theatre was found during municipality-funded preventive archaeological survey for constructing a transport tunnel through the Three Hills of Plovdiv. The site was excavated between 1968-1978 by the Archaeological Museum (L. Botusharova) and the theatre was discovered during the process. Research on the site has continued in 1982-1983 and 2008-2009 (M. Martinova-Kyutova) giving more insight to the history of Philippopolis.

The theatre was built in the late 1st- early 2nd centuries on the southern slope of the Three Hills, where it sits in the area between two southern hills, Dzhambaz tepe and Taxim tepe with the outer diameter of c. 82 m. The theatre is semi-circular and tiered, taking advantage of the natural stone slope. The tiered spectator area can seat c. 3,000 people and was probably used as theatre stage, for gladiator combats and wild beast hunts.

Plovdiv Theatre. © Maya Martinova-Kyutova

The theatre was restored in 1979 and 1981 with the principles of anastylosis, ie using the original architectural elements recovered during the excavations as much as possible and new additions to the structure are clearly observable due to the use of new distinguishable materials. The restoration of the Roman Theatre of Philippopolis is considered one of the best achievements of the Bulgarian Conservation School.

The restored theatre is a popular tourist site managed by the Ancient Plovdiv Municipal Institute and received 63,500 visits in 2019. The Institute, founded in 2004, preserves and promotes Plovdiv heritage and manages 11 heritage sites excavated within the city. Additionally, the theatre is used as a stage for cultural events – there is an annual Opera Open music festival, International Folklore festival, Rock Festival “Sounds of Ages” and many more events.

Publications, links, resources

Martinova-Kyutova, M., Sharankov, N. 2018. The Ancient Theatre of Philippopolis (Plovdiv, Bulgaria). In: Bulletin of The National Archaeological Institute, XLIV (= Proceedings of the First International Roman and Late Antique Thrace Conference “Cities, Territories and Identities”, Plovdiv, 3rd – 7th October 2016). Sofia, 68-76.

Accessible at: series.naim.bg/index.php/BNAI/article/view/47/36

Vagalinski, L. F. 2009. Blood and Entertainments. Sports and Gladiatorial Games in Hellenistic and Roman Thrace. Sofia.

oldplovdiv.bg/en/index

ancient-stadium-plovdiv.eu/

plovdivbg.info/objects/antique-theatre/?lang=en

04.6 BENEFIT 5: REFLECTIVE COMMUNITIES

Development-led archaeology contributes to communal reflection understanding, and reconciliation.

Archaeology provides a setting for personal and communal reflection and understanding. Whether it is an ancient place of worship, the site of a battle or shipwreck, or the place associated with events of great joy or calamity, our archaeological heritage offers us physical touchpoints of great power to consider and reflect upon matters of belief, spirit, identity and memory, and what it is to be human. It contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goals 10 (reduced inequalities) and 16 (peace, justice and strong institutions).

Our case studies show how a lost synagogue can be connected with a Holocaust memorial and museum to create public spaces for memory and reconciliation, and how a nameless cemetery can catalyse political and public discourse about uncomfortable pasts.

CASE STUDY:

Judenplatz, Vienna, Austria

Initial excavations in Judenplatz took place in 1995, in advance of the installation of the remarkable Shoa memorial, designed by Rachael Whiteread to commemorate the loss of Austrian Jews in the Holocaust. During these excavations, parts of the medieval synagogue serving the former Jewish quarter were discovered. In consequence, a rescue excavation took place between 1996 and 1997. Beside the synagogue also remains of the Roman legionary fort and different medieval and modern traces were found. Judenplatz formed the centre of Jewish cultural and religious life in Vienna from around 1280 until the 'Wener Gesera' of 1420/21, when Albert V ordered the annihilation of the city's Jews, and the synagogue was destroyed

Excavations under way in Judenplatz, Vienna.
© Stadtarchäologie Wien/urban archaeology
department of the city of Vienna.

Rachel Whiteread's remarkable Holocaust memorial which sits directly above the Judenplatz synagogue remains. © C.Stadler/Bwag; CC-BY-SA-4.0.

The remains of the synagogue were preserved and incorporated in a new museum. The showroom with the remains of the medieval synagogue on Vienna's Judenplatz is an almost magical place. Visitors descend into the museum, about 7m down to find themselves in an exhibition about Vienna's Jewish community in the middle ages. A further flight of stairs brings them to the synagogue. The archaeological remains are simple to read, although construction details are explained to guests of all ages: that the "synagogue" floor is not in situ, that the foundation and not rising masonry can be seen, that the synagogue had three construction phases and that the bima, the desk from which the Torah is read in synagogues, was hexagonal.

Many visitors, young and old, are surprised that Jewish history in Vienna goes back further than they thought. The fact that the Viennese community was an intellectual and cultural centre in the middle ages, where famous rabbis worked, is also discussed, as is the relationship between the faiths in the city at the time. Archaeological finds such as dishes, the doors of a pocket mirror, coins, a comb and even a toy horse evoke a personal link. The work of archaeologists in Vienna is described. The place invites visitors to reflect on time and history, past and present, one's own and that of others. The excavation area is used by members of the Misrachi community to light the Hanukkah candles while many teachers book a workshop in the Judenplatz Museum as part of traditional religious instruction.

Funder: The archaeological investigation was funded by the City of Vienna.

Archaeological organisation: The excavations were conducted by the urban archaeology department of Vienna which then was part of the office of the Viennese Municipal Council. The head of the department was Univ. Doz. Dr. Ortoľ Harl.

Publications, links, resources

stadtarchaeologie.at/start/publikationen/fundort-wien/fundort-wien-1

stadtarchaeologie.at/?s=Judenplatz

CASE STUDY: Vilnius, Lithuania

The uprising against the Russian Empire in 1863–1864 is one of the most outstanding episodes within the narrative of the Lithuanian 19th-century resistance and struggle for freedom. It was known that 21 participants in the uprising against the Russian Empire had been executed at Lukiškės Square in Vilnius in 1863–1864. In January 2017, during reinforcement groundworks of the slopes of Gediminas Hill, 20 burials thought to be those executed participants were unexpectedly discovered.

The executed participants in the Uprising were buried on the Gediminas Hill for very particular reasons. It was one of the best-fortified sites in Vilnius and has always been one of its outstanding landmarks and symbols. After the Russian Empire occupied and divided the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, there was no public access to the Gediminas Hill after 1794: a Russian artillery squad was deployed there and, after the Uprising of 1831, under the order of Emperor Nicholas I, the Gediminas Hill along with the so-called Hill Park was transformed into a fortress. Public access to this area was forbidden. The site of burial of the executed from the Uprising was selected based on the belief that no-one would be able to gain access to the graves and turn them into a place of public worship and commemoration. Secrecy was important: almost no sources indicated that the participants in the Uprising were buried there.

The discovery of the burial site became a sensation not only within the scientific community but also with the public. It raised public interest not only in the historical events but also in the archaeological science itself, as archaeologists had enabled these discoveries in collaboration with the historians. Numerous interviews in mass media, publications in the press, public debates and newly-published books boosted interest in archaeology and made the historians and, more importantly, the public to rethink the events of the Uprising of 1863–1864 which had been out of the public discourse for some time. Politicians reflected on the issue of insufficient financing of the scientific centres understanding, recognising that fundamental discoveries such as this wouldn't be possible without proper support from the state.

Sculpture Rebels (by Konstantinas Bogdanas) near the exhibition location. © Ričardas Dediala.

Reburial of the participants of the Uprising of 1863–1864 at the Vilnius Rasos Cemetery turned into an event of national importance for all three states that emerged on the territory of the former Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth: the ceremony, held in 2019, was attended not only by the President of Lithuania but also by the President of Poland and Deputy Premier of Belarus. Moreover, ordinary citizens of these countries also arrived to pay their respects to the participants of the Uprising in huge numbers and their coffins were jointly carried by Lithuanian and Polish militaries.

This case has shown that the meticulous work of archaeologists, in cooperation with other scientists, not only renewed and fuelled a state-level historical debate but also elevated the value and importance of the very science of archaeology in the eyes of the public and contributed to the formation of new historical narratives.

Publications, links, resources

Dediala, R. 2021 Archaeology and the History of the Lithuanian Resistance in the 19th and 20th Centuries: in search of the public benefit, *Internet Archaeology* 57.

doi.org/10.11141/ia.57.11.

04.7 BENEFIT 6: LIFELONG LEARNING

Development-led archaeology contributes directly to education at all stages of life.

Archaeology contributes directly to life-long education. Whether through town hall presentations, evening lectures, interaction with school children, a museum visit or a guided tour around a neighbourhood, our archaeological heritage can prompt questions of what, how, why, when and who, inspiring curiosity and galvanising learning, up-skilling and volunteering. It is a vast library of human expression and ingenuity. Developments can create novel and exciting opportunities both during and after the investigations. It contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 (quality education).

Our case study shows how political and administrative drive can open archaeology to the next generation on a grand scale.

CASE STUDY:

The Public Archaeology and Heritage Education Project in Israel

Since 2015, the Israel Antiquities Authority (an observer member of EAC) has instituted a project to change the public attitude towards the remains of the past through mass education. At the core is the active participation of different sectors of Israeli society in exposing the remains of the past, preserving them and making them accessible to the general public. The stated aim of the project is to develop identification with local built heritage and through them create an environment for cultural heritage protection.

The main activity of the project is the integration of thousands of schoolchildren of various ages and high school graduates in various frameworks in the ongoing activities of the Israel Antiquities Authority (IAA), with emphasis on preventative and salvage archaeological excavations.

Combined with actual excavation experience and hands on contact with their country's past, participants also benefit through participating simply in manual labour in the outdoors school, an opportunity that in the days of the air-conditioned classroom, surprisingly few experience. As part of its outreach activities, the project includes activities in social media, creating platforms for seminars and series of lectures open to the general public, and even publishing for the first time a popular Arabic-language journal on archaeology for the general public.

A typical youth group celebrating the discovery of a mosaic inscription, 2020.

Photo: Benjamin Storchan © Israel Antiquities Authority.

The following statistics provide evidence of the impact of the programme for the school year 2017-2018:

- 45,000 participants from 450 educational institutions in all the programmes.
- 250 schools and educational institutions participated in the excavations
- 60 gap year programmes also participated in the project
- 6,000 individuals were involved in the excavations, provided 30,000 work days
- 2,000 pupils took summer jobs as archaeological labourers in the summer of 2018, working for some 12,700 work days.
- 2,000 additional students excavated to provide funds for extra-curricula educational activities.

The work was conducted across the country, with the aim of involving pupils in excavations close to their place of residence. Many of the activities were aimed at minority communities or at providing opportunities for cross-cultural involvement. Specific programmes were instituted to prepare sites for public interpretation:

- Kanaf, Apollonia, Haqoq, Adulam and Mamphis: 63 schools, 5261 pupils
- Jerusalem Walls: 7,000 pupils
- Sanhedrin Path: 45 educational institutions, 8,500 pupils and training of 490 teachers about the project.
- Holocaust study tour to Poland programme: 50 institutions, 1,760 pupils.
- Adopt a Site: 4,000 participants.
- Excavation for Arabic speaking pupils: 3,300 pupils and 70 teachers

For the 2018-2019 school year we provided opportunities for 60,000 participants in the various programmes of the project noted above and instituted a new programme designed for the integration of 'adolescents in danger' (socially deprived youth and youth with problems of truancy and delinquency).

As part of the extra-curricular educational experience, archaeology practice becomes a mediator of history, culture, cross-society interaction and for a few, a life-changing experience, leading some to choose archaeology as a career.

This exposure to archaeology and built heritage leads to a change in the consciousness of various groups in Israeli society towards their own responsibility for remains of the past. We have also found that the appreciation drawn from the project participants for the preservation and sustainability of antiquities has a ripple down effect, as they pass on the message to others around them.

Furthermore, the IAA is aware that the manual work of the participants is an actual contribution to the advancement of its projects. Consequentially many of the participants with longer term commitments to the project are paid for their work, especially in the context of provision for additional educational activities, such as a journeys to Poland as part of a Holocaust study trips or to Ethiopia for pupils of Jewish-Ethiopian descendant.

Publications, links, resources

Storchan, Benyamin (2020), "Israeli teens and their Byzantine church: Community archaeology at the Church of the Glorious Martyr" *Journal of Community Archaeology & Heritage* doi.org/10.1080/20518196.2020.1801299

www.friendsofiasa.org/lod-education

www.youtube.com/watch?v=KMYBtiE6Vlg

04.8 BENEFIT 7: SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION

Development-led archaeology contributes directly to wider science and innovation in other disciplines and fields of study.

Archaeological remains provide very rich and often unique resources for the advancement of a number of scientific disciplines. These are primarily palaeo-biological or palaeo-ecological samples recovered from (for example) human and faunal skeletal remains, plant macrofossils, intact palaeo-environments (waterlogged horizons, peats, palaeosols), sealed or residue-encrusted containers (coffins, glass vessels). They can manifest as fragments of aDNA, molecular evidence, evidence for former species or biovars, evidence for diseases in bone, samples for dendrochronology dating, and more. This potential is of very significant value for the understanding of evolution, biodiversity, the spread of pathogens, the incidence, cause and treatment of diseases, and the understanding of climate change, yet has not been leveraged strategically to any significant degree, relying on ad hoc or happenstance connections between archaeologists and scientists. This benefit contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goals 3 (good health and wellbeing), 9 (industry, innovation and infrastructure), and 13 (climate action).

Our case study shows how one medieval cemetery can give us the tools to understand a killer disease.

CASE STUDY:

The Black Death Cemetery, London, UK

In advance of commercial re-development of the former Royal Mint site at East Smithfield, London, excavations in 1986-7 revealed the location of a mass cemetery of over 700 burials dated to 1348-9. After detailed study by human skeletal archaeologists, these skeletons were retained in the Museum of London's archives and transferred in 2003 to their Centre for Human Bioarchaeology. Since then, they have been available for international peer-reviewed scientific research. After a funding hiatus a monograph on the cemetery was published in 2008 (Grainger et al, 2008).

The palaeopathology of the Black Death has been a debated topic for decades, but the emergence of sophisticated techniques for recovering and mapping ancient DNA (aDNA) has permitted molecular biologists and archaeologists to join forces. Anastasiou and Mitchell (2013) summarise the sequence of events: "In 2010 Haensch et al (2010) used two different techniques (PCR and immunochromatography) to isolate the *pl* gene from the teeth of 76 victims of the Black Death, excavated from the London site, France, Germany, Italy and the Netherlands. The study demonstrated that two different genotypes, ancestral to the *Y. pestis* biovar of *Orientalis* and to the *Y. pestis* biovar of *Medievalis*, were responsible for the Black Death in Medieval Europe.

The site of the Black Death cemetery in 1987, with the Tower of London in the background. Photo: Peter Mills © MOLA.

Then, in 2011, Bos et al (2011) were able to reconstruct the genome of *Y. pestis* ... from victims of the Black Death from ... London. Based on a phylogenetic analysis, the authors concluded that the *Y. pestis* strain extracted from victims of the Black Death is ancestral to most of the extant strains of the disease, and sits very close to the ancestral node of all *Y. pestis* strains that cause human infection. Furthermore, based on temporal estimates, the authors argued that the Black Death of the 14th century AD was the main event that introduced and disseminated the ancestor of all current *Y. pestis* strains infective to humans... It has been argued that the *Y. pestis* increase in virulence during the Black Death may not be related to novel fixed point mutations easily detected with current approaches. Rather, the increased virulence of the Black Death may be the outcome of a synergy of factors, related to the environmental conditions, to the genetics of the host population and to interactions with concurrent diseases (Bos et al, 2011). However, another interpretation is that the virulence of the disease may be affected by other areas of the genome than those currently recognised, and differences in those regions may perhaps explain the dramatic death rates seen in 14th-century outbreaks”.

Closer examination by the archaeogeneticists discovered mutations in some of the aDNA from the later burials at the London cemetery (probably dating to 1361), leading some medical historians and theoretical biologists to suggest the possibility that a new strain of the disease had emerged: "But think about the implications of that: plague arrives in London at the end of 1348 as a new disease, and a new strain (with 3 new SNPs [*Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms*]) is causing a major new outbreak in 1361... which is when this burial seems to date from" (Green and Schmid 2016).

The archive from this London burial ground has attracted repeated international research teams. They have used the aDNA evidence to establish the genome of the bacillus that caused the Black Death and expanded the understanding of how that pathogen evolved. This could have direct consequences for understanding the management of this and other pathogens and modern diseases. The difficulty in isolating and sequencing genetic codes of ancient pathogens such as this has catalysed the development of new techniques for the rapid, accurate recovery of aDNA from archaeological samples (eg Hübler et al 2019). The plague bacillus is just one example of the potential provided by archaeological excavations to give access to entirely new resources for scientific studies of direct relevance to the modern world.

Publications, links, resources

Anastasiou, E, Mitchell, PD, 2013 'Paleopathology and genes: investigating the genetics of infectious diseases in excavated human skeletal remains and mummies from past populations' *Gene* 528(1), 33-40

www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0378111913007701

Bos, KI, Schuenemann, VJ, Golding GB, Burbano, HA, Waglechner, N, Coombes, BK, McPhee, JB, DeWitte, SN, Meyer, M, Schmedes, S, Wood, J, Earn, DJD, Herring, DA, Bauer, P, Poinar, HN, and Krause, J, 2011, 'A draft genome of *Yersinia pestis* from victims of the Black Death' *Nature* 478, 506–510. www.nature.com/articles/nature10549

Grainger, I, Hawkins, D, Cowal, L, and Mikulski, R 2008, *The Black Death Cemetery, East Smithfield, London* MoLAS Monograph 43 (London)

Green, M and Schmid, B 2016 'Plague Dialogues: Monica Green and Boris Schmid on Plague Phylogeny (II)', contagions.wordpress.com/2016/06/29/plague-dialogues-monica-green-and-boris-schmid-on-plague-phylogeny-ii/ accessed 23.11.20

Hübler, R, Key, FM, Warinner, C, Bos, KI, Krause, J, and Herbig, A, 2019 'HOPS: automated detection and authentication of pathogen DNA in archaeological remains' *Genome Biology* volume 20, Article number: 280 genomebiology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13059-019-1903-0

Spyrou, M. A. et al. 2016 Historical *Y. pestis* genomes reveal the European Black Death as the source of ancient and modern plague pandemics. *Cell Host Microbe* 19, 874–881

Spyrou, M. A. et al 2019 Phylogeography of the second plague pandemic revealed through analysis of historical *Yersinia pestis* genomes *Nature Communications* volume 10, Article number: 4470 www.nature.com/articles/s41467-019-12154-0

04.9 BENEFIT 8: HEALTH AND WELLBEING

Development-led archaeology can improve people's physical and mental wellbeing.

Archaeology can have a wide range of beneficial impacts on the physical, mental and social wellbeing of individuals and communities. Evidence shows impacts on individual wellbeing, including outcomes such as increased confidence, social connectivity and life satisfaction. Archaeology can actually be good for us. Development-led archaeology has the potential to provide genuine opportunities to take advantage of these impacts. It contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goal 3 (good health and well-being).

Our case studies show how archaeology can help to rebuild lives and grow self-confidence and wellbeing.

CASE STUDY:

'Archaeological Social Initiative Styria', Austria

ASIST ("Archäologisch-Soziale Initiative Steiermark") is a not-for-profit initiative in the Austrian region of South and West Styria, established in 2006 and funded by the Austrian public employment service (AMS), the European Social Fund and the State of Styria. ASIST works as a gateway between builder-owner/project developer, community, regions, districts, province and state and its focus is on the promotion of employment projects. Long-term unemployed are temporarily employed during development-led excavations in order to help re-integration in work processes. Individual training under supervision help in exploring new chances.

The costs are covered by the AMS, but also from the federal states of Austria, from sponsors, and in some cases from the European Union. The realization of each project is different, depends on the individual structures and economic resources, while the duration of the placements is between 3-8 months.

The Hengist excavation team (2012) uncovering the oldest grave evidence in Styria: from the so-called Lasinja culture. © Kulturpark Hengist / Mrs Martina Trausner

Between 2006 and 2020 ASIST conducted about 25 excavations, including many development-led rescue excavations, such as the excavations at a Nazi forced labour camp in Styria, Bronze Age Settlements at Deutschlandsberg and Pichling, early iron age burial mounds at Großklein. The Bronze Age settlement excavations at Deutschlandsberg included:

- Rescue excavation, Deutschlandsberg, Hörbing, Styria, big housing projects in an area of Bronze Age and Roman settlements: April – May 2018;
- Rescue excavation Deutschlandsberg, Fludergasse, Styria, big housing projects in an area of Bronze Age and Roman settlements: March – April 2019;

Each excavation employed 6 previously unemployed workers (full time employment/38 hours a week, no former qualifications needed), 1 scientific employee (full time), 1 social worker/social pedagogue. The condition for inclusion in the programme was that the workers had been previous long-termed unemployed for at least 6 months. There was no restriction on age, the statistics show that 50% of the participants were over 50 years old, with men and women equally represented. Some of the most usual issues that have reduced the participants' chances to find employment were physical disabilities, alcoholism and drug addiction, together with lack of motivation.

During employment about 20% of working time was used for further education, training and/or coaching with the social pedagogue, working on individual problems. Each project offered employment for 3-6 months. Employment combined with supervision and care by social workers work as a stabilizing factor and provides new perspectives. Further training during the project improved the chances for finding new employment. 20% of the participants successfully found permanent employment after the end of the project¹⁰.

The touristic development resulting from the reconstruction of ruins, monuments and sites is reinforced by the project's publicity and adds to the benefits of the initiative.

Publications, links, resources

www.asist.at

¹⁰ Annual report 2019 of ST:WUK (www.verwaltung.steiermark.at/cms/dokument/11991514_106727595/eefc9dcb/0528_stwuk_JB2019_HP_klein.pdf)

CASE STUDY:**The Use of Archaeological Excavation as a Remedial Intervention for 'At-Risk' Youth in Israel**

At-risk youth suffer from a range of emotional or behavioural problems, drug addiction, high levels of truancy, low academic performance, a disconnection from the school environment and are frequently involved in juvenile delinquency. Often these patterns of behaviour are exacerbated by economic and social disadvantage and dysfunctional families. After the regular school system fails to provide a suitable environment for their continued participation, many at-risk pupils in Israel drop out of schools. Failure to provide care for these pupils pushes them towards delinquent behaviour and even petty crime, the solution being care in various specifically tailored educational frameworks and hostels.

In recent years the Israel Antiquities Authority (IAA) has instituted a large scale educational programme to include regular pupils in archaeological excavation with the aim of changing the public attitude towards the remains of the past through mass education, to develop identification with the archaeological heritage and through them, create an environment for cultural heritage protection.

Together with the instructors and teachers from institutions involved in the provision of education and guidance for at-risk youth, it was decided to include them in excavation activities in development projects as a remedial intervention. Furthermore, manual work of the participants is an actual contribution to the advancement of archaeological projects. Consequentially many of the participants with longer term commitments to the project were paid for their work.

Boys from the Tiberias Hostel and Ramat Hadassah Youth Village participated in 2020 in excavations in Hittin, Tivon and Kishron. These institutions house boys with a history of addictions and are rehabilitative frameworks. In addition to the excavation, the at-risk youth underwent short complementary enrichment activities, including visits to nearby excavations, instruction on how to excavate and a simple explanation on the chronological timeline of the archaeology that they were excavating (in this case an on-site description of the battle between the Crusaders and Saladin at the Horns of Hattin).

The feedback from the activity showed that there were few disciplinary issues, on the contrary the boys behaved impeccably. It was obvious that the boys were happy to be on the site and most of them mentioned the contribution of the excavation for them personally, some asking to dig in similar IAA excavations in the future. The archaeologists involved were initially fearful that the involvement of at-risk youth in high pressured development-based excavations would impede the work, but were pleasantly surprised to find that these pupils quickly absorbed a basic understanding of (supervised) simple excavation techniques and contributed significantly to the success of the excavations, even noting that their work output was often higher than that of regular pupils.

Einat Ambar-Armon and Yair Amizur. © Israel Antiquities Authority.

Feedback received from the institutions noted that they had initial concerns at how the young people would cope with the pressure of the work and the discipline required. However, they noted that the work at the excavation encouraged personal commitment, responsibility, integration in the world of work, leadership, respect for colleagues and self-empowerment (youth who regularly have difficulty getting up in the morning for school woke up independently for a grueling day at five in the morning!).

In conclusion, the integration of at-risk youth in development-based archaeology has a mutual benefit for the excavation and more importantly, for society and the young people themselves.

Publications, links, resources

Ambar-Armon, Einat and Amizur, Yair, in prep 'Changing Consciousness in the Relationship between Man, Community and Archeology' Israel Antiquities Authority

Storchan, Benjamin (2020), "Israeli teens and their Byzantine church: Community archaeology at the Church of the Glorious Martyr" *Journal of Community Archaeology & Heritage*, 8, pp. 91-104

04.10 BENEFIT 9: ECONOMIC GROWTH

Development-led archaeology can contribute direct economic benefits to investors and communities.

Archaeology can contribute direct economic benefits to investors and communities. Inspiring places encourage business and enterprise, which in turn drives up opportunities for local people. Distinctive places drive tourism. Tourism creates footfall which leads to sustainable economies. This benefit contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goal 8 (decent work and economic growth).

Our case study shows how an archaeological 'problem' became the centre-piece of a highly successful commercial venture.

CASE STUDY:

Arena de Serdica hotel, Sofia, Bulgaria

In 2004 construction works of a new hotel in the FairPlay International JSC Hotels & Resorts chain revealed a part of a Roman wall. Archaeological excavations immediately started. Thus the amphitheatre of Roman Serdica (now Sofia – the capital of Bulgaria) was discovered.

The original design of the new hotel was significantly changed to include the revealed eastern part of the amphitheatre, which takes the place of an indoor pool and part of the parking spaces. The implementation of the project was delayed by 6 months and costs increased by about €123,000. However, the fact that the project for the interior of the hotel was re-designed to maximise the integration of the archaeological remains contributed directly to a higher categorization of the hotel.

Serdica / Sofia amphitheatre. © FairPlay International JSC

Since its opening, the hotel has been categorized as a 5 star Residence hotel. This category is awarded to unique accommodation and carries an international recognition. According to the owners, the integration of the Roman amphitheatre is fundamental to the success of the hotel, especially in the guest market which prefers Sofia as a tourist destination. The presence of the amphitheatre within the hotel itself is one of the main reasons for these guests to choose Arena di Serdica Hotel.

This positive trend is even more visible in terms of events. The most preferred place for corporate and image events is the hotel lobby overlooking the structural remains. The transformation of an archaeological monument into an event location is extremely pleasing to the organizers of quality events. Hotel Arena di Serdica has been chosen for a number of events, including those of national importance and great media coverage. During the summer months, when Sofia is usually full of tourists, the hotel is visited daily by guests who are not accommodated in it. These tourists want to enjoy the view in the lobby, which makes them customers of the lobby bar. The good financial results have motivated the owners to create a foundation for the socialization of other archaeological sites around. The hotel works entirely at its own expense with guides, tour operators and travel agents so that the amphitheatre can be present in all tours and promotional materials for Sofia. The hotel also participates in the annual European “Night of Museums” to present itself as a museum.

Publications, links, resources

www.arenadiserdica.com/arena-di-serdica-residence-hotel-sofia/pages/the-amphiteater-of-ancient-serdica

ulpiaserdica.com/amphitheatre_bg.html

www.goethe.de/ins/bg/de/kul/the/sta/20880259.html

www.youtube.com/watch?v=K2Nt6f7ugv4

www.youtube.com/watch?v=08lufIFzld8 https://www.academia.edu/42041549/Blood_and_Entertainments_Sports_and_Gladiatorial_Games_in_Hellenistic_and_Roman_Thrace

ANNEX 1

Summary of legislative instruments governing archaeological heritage management in some member states of the European Archaeological Council. Correct in 2019.

Desislava Gradinarova (EAC Assistant in 2019)

In August 2019 The European Archaeological Council (EAC) ran a survey of its members about the legal and practical aspects of making the case for the public benefit derived from development-led (rescue) archaeology. In our survey we asked:

“What key piece of current legislation requires archaeological investigation as part of development, and, briefly, what is the given reason for that piece of legislation?”

These are some of the examples that EAC members provided as to what relevant national legislation controls the development-led archaeology in a range of European countries:

Austria: Monument protection Act (DMSG) § 8 and 9 that define, that a find leads to protection by law until the Authority decides whether to uphold this protection – therefore investigation might be necessary. Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfungsgesetz (Law on EIA) that enable the Authority to require interventions. Raumordnungsgesetz (zoning processes) that delimitate archaeological sites and monuments, so indication, where §§8 and 9 of the DMSG are likely to be applied.

Belgium – Flanders: On January 1st 2015 a new immovable heritage decree, bundling and updating all the legislation concerning the built heritage, landscapes and archaeology, has entered into force in Flanders. The decrees chapter concerning archaeology was fully effective from June 2016 on. The new law reaffirms certain principles already included in the older legislation, updates them and strengthens their effectiveness, and introduces new ones. Most importantly it aims at the full implementation of the Valletta-Convention.

Research is central to the archaeological process. The Immovable Heritage Decree distinguishes three routes that this research can follow. Either the research is linked to spatial developments as an obligation, or it is of a scientific nature, or it takes place as a result of activities accidentally affecting archaeological sites. Archaeological research comprises both preliminary archaeological research (without or with intervention in the soil) and archaeological excavations. A permission is always required to carry out a preliminary archaeological investigation involving intervention in the soil and archaeological excavations. In addition, specific reporting obligations apply to each process via the archaeology note, the note, the archaeology report or the final report. The initiators, recognized archaeologists, the licensing authorities, the Agency for Immovable Heritage, the recognized immovable heritage municipalities and inter-municipal immovable heritage services are the main players in the archaeological process. Their role and mission vary according to the route taken.

Chapter 5 of the new regulation and more specific articles 5.4.1 and 5.4.2 define the surface criteria that determine in advance (before granting the building permit) the need for archaeological research. The “recognized” archaeologist draws up his own plan of action for archaeological research. Once submitted, the Flemish government screens his proposal.

Bulgaria: A new Cultural Heritage Act was adopted in 2009.

According to Art. 2a (1) of the CHA: "Cultural values, archaeological sites and objects originating from the territory and the territorial waters of the Republic of Bulgaria, are public state property".

According to Art. 148 (5) of the CHA: "The resources needed for rescue fieldwork, until the complete research of the land, shall be provided by the contracting authority whose investment initiative is related to the rescue research."

According to Art. 161 (1) of the CHA: "The implementation of investment projects of natural persons and legal entities within territories for which there are data about the presence of archaeological sites shall be preceded by preliminary archaeological investigations, which shall determine whether they will be affected or damaged. Rescue excavations shall be conducted on the archaeological sites uncovered during these investigations, prior to the start of construction works."

(2) "In the course of construction works, archaeologists shall carry out monitoring. In case of discovery of archaeological sites, Articles 148 and 160 shall be applied." i.e. the construction shall be stopped and an archaeological field research shall be conducted.

The Regulation on Conducting Archaeological Fieldwork (2011) was supplemented by a **state tariff (2012)**, according to which the budget of each archaeological field research - rescue or regular / planned, observation, excavation or non-destructive research, is formed.

Czechia: The most important are:

Act No. 20/1987 on state landmark conservation: § 2 - § 6 define types of protected sites

Act No. 183/2006 on Spatial Planning and Building Code: § 2, § 11, § 18: defines Archaeological heritage as a subject of public interest that must be respected during the spatial planning process.

Denmark: The Danish Museum Act of 2001 (§ 27) claims that when archaeological structures (defined as in the Valetta Convention) are met during constructing activities etc. the work must be stopped, the structures evaluated and archaeological excavation carried out if needed. The law also describes a procedure for evaluation work prior to the construction phases (including early involvement in the (official) planning phase and pre-construction archive- and field-work), but these parts are all voluntary (cf. §§ 23-24 (official planning), §§ 25-26 (private planning and evaluation work)).

The changes in the law from 2001 were for a large part made to ratify the Valetta Convention - including the "in situ" protection of sites (though, a somehow similar view was expressed also in the former Museum Act). The "Polluter Pay-principle" was on the other introduced in the 2001-law (in fact with the hope, that it would mean less excavations to support the "in situ" protection-principle - with never became the case).

Estonia: In Estonia, it is the new Heritage Conservation Act (in force since May 1st 2019), a law intended to protect all types of heritage-related monuments, among which archaeological monuments, archaeological sites and areas where the Heritage Board has information about possible archaeological layer.

*§ 11 (3) An archaeological monument is the remains, thing or set of things of human activity and other traces which indicate the multiple layers of time on a cultural landscape and which provide scientific information on the history of mankind and human relations with the natural environment. An archaeological layer is an important part of an archaeological monument.
Protection and termination of protection of protected archaeological site*

§ 25 (1) A protected archaeological site is an area or land or water, where archaeological finds, human bones, remains of historical building structures or other elements referring to an archaeological layer have been found and which may still contain such elements.

§ 31 (3) An archaeological research shall be conducted in the course of environmental impact assessment for the purposes of the Environmental Impact Assessment and Environmental Management System Act on an immovable where according to the information of the Board, based on historical sources, there may be archaeological objects, human bones or an archaeological layer. The provisions of §§ 46–48 of this Act shall be applied to the determination and conduct of research. The expenses of the given research shall not be reimbursed pursuant to subsection 48 (2) of this Act.

Link to English translation: www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/504062019001/consolide

Finland: The Antiquities Act (295/63; Chapter 1); Ancient monuments are protected by law as antiquities pertaining to the past settlement and history of Finland.

Without permission stipulated in this Act, it is forbidden to excavate, cover, alter, damage or remove ancient monuments, or to disturb them in any other way.

§ 13: In the planning of public roads, railways, canals, airports, waterworks or other public works or in the preparation of urban or zone plans, those responsible shall establish in sufficient time beforehand whether the execution of such works or plans will concern ancient monuments. If this is the case, the Finnish Heritage Agency must be informed thereof without delay to arrange necessary negotiations. The statement of the landowner concerned shall be noted in said negotiations.

§ 15: Where the execution of public or considerable private works concern an ancient monument insofar as they require special investigations of said monument or special action to preserve it, the party responsible for the works shall defray the costs arising therefrom or remunerate part of them, unless this requirements is deemed unreasonable under the prevailing circumstances.

Germany (Bonn): Monument Protection Law of North Rhine-Westphalia [DSchG NRW] (1980, amended 2013)

All archaeological monuments in North Rhine-Westphalia (defined in § 2 (1) & (5) DSchG NRW) receive special protection status by § 3 DSchG NRW (listed monuments) and § 29 DSchG NRW (specific properties suspected of containing archaeological monuments). Spatial planning has to be in accordance to § 1 (3) and the responsible authorities have to be involved. Any alteration of an archaeological monument requires permission by the responsible authorities (§ 9 DSchG NRW). Also any archaeological excavation requires permission by § 13 DSchG NRW.

Hungary: Before the development all archaeological sites must be excavated due to the Cultural Heritage law (2001. 64.) net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0100064.TV

The Hungarian archaeological approach to preventive archaeology is essentially based on two major principles: 1) archaeological artefacts found in the ground are state property; 2) it is of public interest to protect and excavate the archaeological heritage under threat – therefore everything has to be excavated. The implementation of the Valetta Convention was undertaken in 2001 in Hungary and revised several times. As compulsory documentation prior to large developments, archaeology was integrated into the planning process. The ‘polluter pays’ principle was a fundamental element of the legislation. The continuous price and time reduction moved the Hungarian archaeology towards non-destructive, GIS-based site identification methods. Additionally, the extending develop-friendly approach resulted in the appearance of predictive archaeological models, which offer a handful and cost-effective tools to estimate archaeological costs. These new (2013) rules also affected the appearance of a complex Preliminary Archaeological Documentation for large investments which contains the identified cultural heritage elements, suggested action plans and financial calculations. (These are all set in the law mentioned above.)

Iceland: The Cultural Heritage Act no. 80/2012

A law passed by the Icelandic government to protect the cultural heritage in Iceland.

Section 16 states that all areas that are about to be planned as well as construction areas (within older planning for example) must be surveyed and cultural heritage (archaeological sites older than 100 years old) registered.

According to sections 22 and 23 no one may disturb, destroy or alter any archaeological heritage site unless permitted by the Cultural Heritage Agency.

Ireland: The Planning and Development Acts and Regulations

Section 10 Content of development plans (1) A development plan shall set out an overall strategy for the proper planning and sustainable development of the area of the development plan and shall consist of a written statement and a plan or plans indicating the development objectives for the area in question.

(c) the conservation and protection of the environment including, in particular, the archaeological and natural heritage and the conservation and protection of European sites and any other sites which may be prescribed for the purposes of this paragraph

(e) the preservation of the character of the landscape where, and to the extent that, in the opinion of the planning authority, the proper planning and sustainable development of the area requires it, including the preservation of views and prospects and the amenities of places and features of natural beauty or interest;

Section 23 Content and objectives of regional planning guidelines (1) (a) The objective of regional planning guidelines shall be to provide a long-term strategic planning framework for the development of the region for which the guidelines are prepared.

(2) The guidelines shall address, for the whole of the region to which the guidelines relate, in accordance with the principles of proper planning and sustainable development, the following matters—

(i) the preservation and protection of the environment and its amenities, including the archaeological, architectural and natural heritage

The Planning And Development Regulations

Section 28 Notice to certain bodies

(I) Where a planning authority receives a planning application, the authority shall, except in the case of an application in respect of which a notice in accordance with article 26(5) has been or will be given, send notice in accordance with sub-article (2) as soon as may be after receipt of the application—

(iii) might affect or be unduly close to-

- (I) a cave, site, feature or other object of archaeological, geological, scientific, ecological or historical interest,
- (II) a monument or place recorded under section 12 of the [National Monuments \(Amendment\) Act, 1994](#) (No. 17 of 1994),
- (III) a historic monument or archaeological area entered in the Register of Historic Monuments under Section 5 of the [National Monuments \(Amendment\) Act, 1987](#) (No. 17 of 1987)
- (IV) a national monument in the ownership or guardianship of the Minister for Arts, Heritage, Gaeltacht and the Islands under the National Monuments Acts, 1930 to 1994

Israel: 'The Law of Antiquities 1978' and especially clauses 28 and 29 of that law, which state: "The Director (of the Israel Antiquities Authority) may declare a particular place to be an antiquity site. ... A person shall not carry out, or allow to be carried out, any of the following on an antiquity site, save with the written approval of the Director and in accordance with the conditions thereof: building, paving, the erection of installations, quarrying, mining, drilling, flooding, the clearing away of stones, ploughing, planting, or interment etc. ... or any other operation designated by the Director in respect of a particular site.

See: www.antiquities.org.il/Article_eng.aspx?sec_id=42&subj_id=228&id=453

Lithuania: Cases of archaeological investigation, excavation methodology, accounting, etc. are regulated by the Heritage Management Regulation "Management of Archaeological Heritage".

Luxembourg: The current legislation does not require any archaeological investigation as part of construction projects. The only requirement is to report fortuitous discoveries to the mayor of the commune they were made in, who is then responsible for the provisory conservation of the finds and has to inform the minister of Culture, who will then state about the fate of the discovery. This would in most cases lead to a temporary building freeze. To avoid this, the CNRA has done large awareness and sensibilisation campaigns, so that a lot of developers now cooperate (voluntarily) with the CNRA in order to avoid delays in their building projects.

The Convention of La Valette did only come into force in August 2017, as Luxembourg was the last signing state. A new project of law introduced in July 2019 will hopefully change the above practice and make archaeological investigations part of the planning procedures.

All works on sites classified as national monument have to get an approval of the Minister of Culture who can attach conditions to the approval such as archaeological excavations, or may reject the application.

Netherlands: In 2007 a law passed by the Dutch government concerning archaeological heritage (Wet op de archeologische Monumentenzorg Wamz) was fundamental for the current archaeological heritage management. Local government was responsible for making rules to protect archaeological sites. This law changed the Monumentenwet 1988 by adding some key articles about protecting archeological sites. (artikel 37 – artikel 45 Monumentenwet) In 2016 the old Monumentenwet was renewed by the Erfgoedwet. In a few years the key legislation about development and archaeology will be in the Omgevingswet. But until that law is in effect (ap. 2012), the key legislation is Artikel 9 Erfgoedwet.

wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0037521/2017-09-01

Norway: The Norwegian Cultural Heritage Act (NCHA) (www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/cultural-heritage-act/id173106/) automatically protects all archaeological monuments and sites – unknown as well as known – predating 1537 (and Sami sites predating 1917). Further, the NCHA generally regulate any activity which can influence on such sites, and states that it is illegal to initiate any measure which is liable to damage or disturb such sites, without permission from the authorities.

The reason for this legislation can be found in the first paragraph:

“The purpose of this Act is to protect archeological and architectural monuments and sites, and cultural environments in all their variety and detail, both as part of our cultural heritage and identity and as an element in the overall environment and resource management.

It is a national responsibility to safeguard these resources as scientific source material and as an enduring basis for the experience of present and future generations and for their self-awareness, enjoyment and activities.

The intention of this Act must also be taken into account in any decision taken pursuant to another Act that may affect the cultural heritage.”

Poland: The Act of 23rd of July on the protection and the guardianship of monuments based on the Valletta Convention. The Convention was ratified by Poland in 1996 and is a part of our legal system.

Sweden: Archaeological heritage is protected by the Historic Environment Act

Section 12 -13 in the second chapter states that a developer who wants to remove an archaeological site must apply to the county administrative board for permission. As conditions for a permission, the county administrative board may impose reasonable demands for example that an archaeological excavation needs to be carried out in order to document the ancient remains, recover ancient finds and communicate the results.

UK: The Town and Country Planning Act 1990 (TCPA) is the principal mechanism for regulating development-led archaeology in England and Wales and is supported, in England, by the National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF). This recognises that archaeology can: add value to a development, for example, by strengthening its distinctive character; make discoveries accessible that would otherwise be lost, contributing to local, national and international stories about our past and informing future research; reduce financial, regulatory and reputational risks for developers, when undertaken at the appropriate stage; benefit local communities by improving public understanding about an area, filling gaps in our knowledge; and present opportunities for the community to participate actively with archaeology as part of a heritage strategy for a site.

In Scotland, development-led archaeology is regulated the Town and Country Planning (Development Management) (Scotland) Regulations 2008, and by Planning Advice Note 2/2011 Planning and Archaeology.

The Ancient Monuments and Archaeological Areas Act 1979 (UK) - This law, passed by the UK government to protect the archaeological heritage of England & Wales and Scotland, defines (sect 61 (12)) sites that warrant protection due to their being of national importance as '*ancient monuments*'. These can be either formally scheduled monuments or any other monument which in the opinion of the Secretary of State is of public interest by reason of the historic, architectural, traditional, artistic or archaeological interest attaching to it.

In Northern Ireland, development-led archaeology is regulated by the Planning Act (Northern Ireland) 2011, supported by Development and Archaeology: Guidance on Archaeological Works in the Planning Process (Department of Communities, 2019). The impacts of development on archaeology is a material consideration in the determination of planning applications with specific policy protections in place. Planning conditions requiring the mitigation of impacts upon archaeological remains may be included in planning permissions. Mitigation strategies may include preservation of remains in situ or archaeological excavation. Advice on the potential impacts of development activity on the historic environment are assessed by professional archaeologists in the Department for Communities as a Statutory Consultee in the consideration of spatial planning decisions. The conduct of the excavations are controlled by a licence, issued under the provisions of the Historic Monuments and Archaeological Objects (Northern Ireland) Order 1995.

